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CONCEPTUALIZATION OF PRODUCT SOUNDS LEARNING FROM MINDMAPS

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ABSTRACT

Conceptual designing for product sounds is a very recent activity within the design teams. Sound designers are not well-equipped to face the challenges of the conceptualization phase. Interpreting an abstract idea (e.g., sporty or cute) in terms of concrete auditory features is not straightforward. Sound designers have to make a link between the abstract and the concrete concepts. Therefore, in this paper mind-maps are presented as a sound sketching tool for (sound) designers to deconstruct the meaning of a desired experience and determine the relevant auditory features. Furthermore, the results of a student workshop that incorporated mind-maps are discussed in terms of the following: 1) are mind-maps an inspirational tool for the initial phase of sound sketching? 2) can they provide insights into the mental representation of abstract product concepts? and finally 3) how are abstract and concrete product concepts are semantically related for auditory experience?

Keywords: conceptual design, product sounds, abstract concepts

INTRODUCTION

People are surrounded by products that emit sounds when functioning (e.g., shavers, cars, hairdryers). These sounds, in principle, can be designed to contribute to the desired experience determined for the product (Blauert & Jekosch, 1997). For example, a car manufacturer such as BMW ensures that their car-engines sound sporty and sophisticated as much as they look so; Philips silences their bagless vacuum-cleaners for comfort; or Grolsch beer-bottles produce the perfect 'plop' sound for fun. However,

product sounds are actually not designed but improved. Designing requires an a priori creative process incorporating idea generation and conceptual thinking that give rise to implementation (Cross, 2000). This process is called conceptualization. Designers skip such major process during sound development due to lack of established practices (Özcan, 2008). This paper discusses what conceptualization means for product sound design and suggests a new but a familiar creative method (i.e., mind-mapping) to encourage and inspire designers to actually design sounds. Furthermore, mind-mapping during sound sketching activity will be discussed in terms of challenges and benefits and its capacity to deconstruct product sound experience into meaningful elements. The results of a workshop on mind-mapping for product sound will be presented.

CHALLENGES DURING CONCEPTUAL DESIGNING

Conceptualization is a creative process that incorporates designers' idiosyncratic and perhaps intuitive interpretation of the desired experience (e.g., sportive and sophisticated). The ultimate goal with conceptual designing is to unravel the conceptual representation of a desired product experience and re-construct it by giving form to the underlying conceptual structure of the experience. At this stage of product development, designers perform cognitive as well as perceptual activities in order to understand the semantic and consequently physical constraints of a desired product experience (Purcell & Gero, 1998). Both cognitive and perceptual activities occur in order to embody abstract and high-level design ideas in tentative forms such as sketches. Sketching provides an iterative platform on which designers can concretize

and formalize their conceptual thoughts on the desired experience (Oxman, 2002). For example, designing a sportive car requires that the designer understands what sporty means and is able to translate an abstract idea into the properties of a car during sketching (e.g., designers may choose an aerodynamic geometry, bright colours and energetic sound to create a sportive car).

Designers think and reinterpret with the emerging images during sketching (Oxman, 2002). Sketching is neither limited to pen-and-pencil drawings nor exclusive to visualization (Ferguson, 1992; Özcan & Sonneveld; 2009). It has been widely acknowledged that sketching in particular and conceptualization in general involve sensory, motor and semantic systems, through which a transaction of ideas occur and sensory imagery is activated (see, e.g., Kavakli & Gero, 2001; Purcell & Gero, 1998). Therefore, sketches can take any visual, tactile, or auditory form that is a part of mock-ups, annotations, small-scale models, narratives, acting-outs.

Conceptual thinking is very complex; interpreting a desired experience and putting ideas into sketching is often not straightforward. The activity of sketching starts in the mind of a designer and mysteriously a (multi-sensory) form emerges. Özcan and Sonneveld (2009) demonstrated that designers go through an embodied exploration process in order to understand a product experience and actually start creating multi-sensory form. For example, they act out by putting themselves in the mood of the experience; they find a proper metaphor to work out the salient features of an experience; they visit a location in which a particular experience occurs the most; or they pay special attention to sensory qualities of objects while interacting with them to determine what sensory properties lead to an experience. All these explorations are done in order

to evoke imagery concerning the product experience in question. However, not much is known at what levels the imagery occurs and how imagery is further used in the embodiment of the product sketches. As demonstrated here, the challenges with conceptual designing are that before starting to sketch, designers may want to have a good understanding of the concept (i.e., product experience) they are working on. Some designers do this intuitively; others need a systematic approach. In either case, it is interesting for the field of design research to understand the constituents of such mysterious mental process and come up with a tool / method to harness the creativity of designers in the very beginning of conceptualization of ideas by encouraging them to delve into the meaning of concepts.

ABSTRACT AND CONCRETE PRODUCT CONCEPTS

Product experience as a design term refers to abstract concepts in cognitive linguistics. Fundamentally, then, designers are dealing with two different types of concepts in order to create a particular experience for a product: abstract concepts which refer to the meaning of experience and concrete concepts which refer to the physical product properties (i.e., tangible, audible, visible properties) of a product (c.f., Murphy, 1996; Lakoff & Johnson, 1980; Paivio, 1986). It is not straightforward for designers to conduct such translations from a meaning domain to a product domain during conceptual design. Mainly because, abstract concepts are considered as implicit knowledge that is difficult to verbally explain, describe, and reproduce from memory (Graesser & Clark, 1985). They are dissociated from any specific instance, not holistically represented in sensory memories, and therefore miss prototypical referents.

Figure 1. A quick search in Google images shows objects that are described as sportive.

Concrete concepts, however, have direct links to sensory, motor and semantic systems which makes their imagery easily accessible and their reproduction in 2D/3D forms possible. As shown in Figure 1, all cars, for example, have distinguishable features as a car (concrete concept), whereas sportive is just one feature of a car (abstract concept), as it is also a feature to a sink faucet, a watch, and a motorbike.

Although abstract concepts do not have fixed referents, they can still simulate sensory representations. Because, they are learnt in daily interactions with objects and their representation is thereby grounded in sensory systems (Barsalou & Wiemer-Hastings, 2005; Goldstone & Barsalou, 1998; Mahon & Caramazza, 2008). Thus, abstract concepts can hold situational information such as time and location but also relevant objects/people in action. Furthermore, they can even elicit emotions (hedonic valence) which can indicate the beneficial function of a situation (Gelenberg, 1997). Sportive, for example, is experienced in various 'exciting' situations (e.g., watching competitions, by being actively involved with sports, purchasing sports goods in stores) through several objects/people that feel, look, sound sportive (e.g., Formula 1 car, running shoes, athletes). With this collective knowledge of instances then one can deduce whether or not a freshly designed product exudes sportiness.

Although abstract concepts are considered not having any instances of a category, the aforementioned situational information (i.e., objects, people, actions, time, location, emotions) can be considered as the instances of abstract concepts. Özcan and Sonneveld's study (2009) on multi-sensory product conceptualization demonstrated that designers look for these instances in their embodied explorations into the meaning of an abstract concept. However, conceptual processing may not be able to directly activate these instances. Dunabeitia and colleagues (Dunabeitia, Aviles, Afonso, Scheefers, & Carreiras, 2009) suggests that abstract concepts first activate other abstract concepts that are semantically similar (e.g., sportive would activate playful, healthy, energetic) compared to the concrete concepts that would immediately activate categorical knowledge (e.g., car would

activate bike and motor-bike). Because the construction of meaning for an abstract concept takes several instances, designers may need to activate a network of associations in order to pinpoint the instances that would inspire them during sketching.

Thus, interpretation of abstract concepts would not be not direct during sketching and has to go through a conceptual network activated by the desired product experience. Fundamentally, it is interesting to know what the constituents of the product experience are and how are these elements are related in order to come up with an inspirational tool for designers.

CONCEPTUALIZATION OF PRODUCT SOUNDS

So far, in this paper conceptualization has been discussed in general terms. It is necessary to adapt such characteristics of conceptualization, to the special needs of product sound conceptualization. As sound is an integral property of a product, theoretically, the rules and methods applied to conceptual designing of a product experience should apply to conceptual designing of product sounds (e.g., deconstructing the meaning of a desired experience and determining the sensory correlates). However, in practice, product sound design requires special attention to the peculiarities of sound and its relation to other sensory properties of a product. The challenges with and during product conceptualization have been demonstrated in the previous sections. With product sound conceptualization challenges are even greater because there are no established tools and methods for product sound sketching, which leaves sound designers unequipped to perform such complex conceptualization activities. However, it is important for sound designers to perform a sketching activity as it will facilitate the further stages of sound design and will make sound more incorporated in the design decisions taken for the overall product (Özcan & van Egmond, 2006; Özcan & Sonneveld, 2009). Thus, sound sketching should be encouraged within the design teams.

Furthermore, auditory memory for product sounds does not work as efficiently as visual memory for the visual form of the product (Özcan & van Egmond, 2007). Product sounds have better links to their

semantic representation then their perceptual representation. That is, it is easier to recall the source names of the sound than to recall how the source sounds. Remembering the spectral-temporal structure of a sound is crucial during sound sketching, as sketching, by nature, incorporates both perceptual and cognitive activities simultaneously. Sound designers, accordingly, need a method that facilitates the retrieval of the spectral-temporal structure of the sound.

As with all kinds of sketching, the ultimate goal of sound sketching is to find auditory links that may underlie the desired experience. For example, if an aerodynamic shape were often found proper for the visual sketches of a sporty car, the loud roaring sound of the engine would best represent a sporty car in a sounding sketch. Thus, for sound designers it is important to determine the quality of the sound (e.g., roaring sound like a powerful lion) that evokes the desired experience and then to analyze what sound properties best constitute a roaring sound (e.g., high-intensity, roughness, temporal pattern). It is these very sound properties that are taken further for the embodiment of the product sounds (i.e., to create an engine sound that is as powerful as a lion roar). Thus, in the basic form of sound sketching, designers first look for objects that can metaphorically represent the desired effect with their sounds (see also Özcan & Sonneveld, 2009).

Jansen and colleagues (Jansen, Özcan & van Egmond, 2010) have focused on the step after by providing designers an interactive tool (PSST! Product Sound Sketching Tool) with which they can explore the effect created by the selected sound properties on the spot. Before using PSST!, designers know the desired effect and also have determined the relevant auditory links. With PSST!, designers use a real-time sound synthesis engine with an appropriate sound parameter set. The sound parameters, in general terms, include: a timbre controller (a granular synthesis with roughness modules), a sound volume controller (an attack-sustain-release envelop), and frequency controllers (low-frequency oscillators; pitch shifting, and shelf-filters for sharpness). The parameters that Jansen et al. used also covered the psycho-acoustical phenomena (loudness, roughness, sharpness,

tonality). According to Özcan (2008), these psychoacoustical parameters characterize product sounds as being either too sharp and loud, or too noisy with accents on the low frequencies; temporal aspects differ from sound to sound as being cyclic (e.g. washing machine sound) to constant (e.g., hairdryer sound) or impulsive (e.g., knobs, power buttons).

Sounds heard in everyday situations automatically activate a conceptual network, which is not limited to lexical representation of sounds (Orgs, Lange, Dombrowski, & Heil, 2007). That is, abstract notion as well as high-level categorical knowledge can be activated upon hearing an environmental sound. Product sounds are a subcategory of environmental sounds. According to Özcan (2008) the conceptual network activated by product sounds derive from two main physical domains, the product and its sound. This conceptual network consists of product as sound source (hairdryer), product properties (small-sized portable hairdryer), type of action causing the sound (air blowing), location in which the product sound is heard (bathroom), abstract meanings (feminine). Furthermore, product sounds can evoke sensory pleasantness (i.e., psychoacoustics) or elicit emotions (e.g., obtrusive, irritating).

Conceptualization of product sounds concerns auditory experience. In real life situations, the presence of sound triggers a chain of reactions (sensory experience, conceptual activation, emotional responses) leading to meaning attribution. Sensory experience is an involuntary response to the physical quality of the product sound. Many sensorial responses are based on basic affects and basic percepts. For example, loud sounds that have increasing pitch and rhythmic structure will be perceived as urgent and unpleasant. These percepts yield a further conceptual activation containing semantic knowledge on sound source, action, location, temporal structure, and abstract meanings. Emotional responses can also occur at this stage. The specificity of the conceptual activation depends on the available context, and with the limitation of the context the most salient concepts stay activated resulting in meaning attribution.

The result of the meaning attribution is dependent on the auditory quality of the sound, namely the

spectral-temporal composition. Thus, sound designers need to assign the right auditory quality to the sound they are designing, which as suggested in this paper should be a result of a sketching process. In practice it is very often that designers intuitively seek form during sketching (pen-pencil, mock-ups) without having thoroughly and systematically analyzed the semantic content of the experience and its links to physical product properties. As Ferguson (1992) has suggested designers think and reason with sketches. However, such intuitive approaches to product sound sketching may not be applicable as sound sketching activity is underpracticed and requires appropriate tools and methods. Furthermore, sound is a time-dependant phenomenon on which is complicated to observe immediate effects while sketching. Thus, sound designers need a systematic approach to start sketching.

In order to do that, the focus of a sound designer should shift from the auditory quality to the desired effect. In daily practices (as observed by psychologists), auditory experience starts with a sound and ends with an effect on people; in between perceptual and cognitive analysis of the sound takes place and semantic associations are automatically activated. In design practice, the effect is known but form (auditory quality) needs to be created by the designer. Therefore, auditory experience should be tackled in reverse order by starting with the effect and then determining the auditory quality. Consequently, the semantic activation to be analyzed in auditory experience should be triggered by the effect (but not by the auditory quality as psychological approaches would suggest). The emergence of auditory quality depends highly on how the designer interprets the desired effect (i.e., abstract concept). Such interpretation is a result of a semantic activation idiosyncratic to the designer; because, abstract concepts are formed in one's daily interactions with objects in certain situations. However, designers may show commonalities in the way which they interpret these concepts. Thus, the mental representation of an abstract concept may consist of certain basic elements such as objects, locations, actions, time, and emotions. The exact constitution of abstract concepts cannot be readily predicted. However, knowing the basic

elements that constitute an abstract concept may help sound designers to systematically deconstruct the meaning of the desired effect and determine the corresponding auditory links. Mind-maps are often used to understand such complex phenomena. Therefore, the following section will discuss how mind-maps can be useful for sound design sketching.

USE OF MIND-MAPS DURING CONCEPTUAL DESIGNING

A mind-map is an idiosyncratic reflection of the conceptual knowledge. It is a graphical tool for representing semantically related items and helps people to generate, visualize, structure, and classify ideas. According to Wikipedia, mind-maps can have various context of application and are mostly used for brainstorming, problem solving, enhancing creativity, making decisions, and organizing information. Buzan (2000) coins the term for modeling complex human thinking. Other methods, more oriented to linguistics, include concept maps and knowledge maps (O'Donnel, Dansereau, & Hall, 2002) or semantic networks. These methods make annotated links between semantically related items and create causal, whole-part, hierarchical, and cross relationships. For education purposes, Oxman (2004) proposed think maps, which are conceptual maps used to develop a tool for taking notes to enhance design thinking among students. Among designers and design students mind-maps are commonly used as a practical way of analyzing design problems, brainstorming, and presenting ideas. Mind-maps fit designerly purpose better compared to the afore-mentioned conceptual and knowledge maps as design problems are often ill-defined problems which lack systematic approaches.

MIND-MAPS FOR DECONSTRUCTING MEANING

In Figure 2, a student uses a mind-map to describe sustainability in terms of product features during her conceptual design phase. As can be seen, the mind-map centers the concept in question and creates branches stemming from the centre. These branches end up as nodes and each node is connected to another node. A node represents a semantic association and is conceptually related to the previous node. Every branch with its nodes characterizes the abstract concept in a unique way.

Thus, with every node the meaning of an abstract idea is deconstructed and explicated making implicit knowledge explicit. Later nodes can be used as features for the re-design of the product. This mind-map in Figure 2 is a result of a student assignment that was provided by the author during the Product Use Understanding and Experience course, which is attended by 120 master level students a year at Delft University of Technology, Faculty of Industrial Design Engineering. The assignment was to describe sustainability in terms of product features for the re-design of a product. All the participating students have provided such a mind-map with some variations. Some described sustainability with images and text; some provided multi-sensory examples as the last nodes to explicate sustainability; some provided more branches, some provided more nodes. However, all students managed to use mind-maps as an inspiring tool for the initial phase of sketching. That is, they used the last nodes (physical object descriptions) as a starting

point for assigning product features during sketching. This figure exemplifies that it takes several consecutive steps for designers to discover the features to be assigned to a product. The occurring features in the mind-maps are often multi-sensory in nature. Thus, these multi-sensory features provide evidence that abstract concepts are embodied in the sensory systems and have references to concrete objects. These concrete objects may constitute the instances of abstract concepts. The consecutive steps in each branch in the mind-maps may be explorations into determining instances of an abstract concept. Therefore, for the translation from the abstract to concrete, designers may need a stepwise conceptual elaboration that systematically unravels possible instances of both abstract and concrete concepts. Furthermore, the occurrence of the sensory features supports the aim of this paper that mind-maps can be used to explore auditory features. For this paper, mind-maps are used for the following

Figure 2. Student, Jitske Menting, describes sustainability in terms of product features (2009).

reasons: 1) to check with sound designers whether mind maps are actually an inspirational tool for the initial phase of sound sketching; and if so, 2) to observe the strategies used to deconstruct the desired auditory experience, and 3) to analyze the type of instances provided in order to determine the constituents of abstract concepts used for auditory experience. In the following section, how students use mind-maps for sound design will be investigated.

MIND-MAPS FOR SOUND SKETCHING EXERCISE

The master level students of Multi-Sensory Design and Sound Design courses at the Faculty of Industrial Design Engineering participated in a workshop to learn how to sketch and design product sounds. Eighteen students were present at the workshop. Part of the assignment they received included the mind-map exercise. The students could freely choose a product and a sound to study. There were several examples of domestic appliances, office supplies, toys, and warning signals. The type of the sound and also the product was not interesting for this study. The focus was on the auditory experience the students intended to create.

The students were asked to choose one desired experience for the re-design of a product sound they were studying. The chosen experience were as follows: help (7x), laidback (2x), mature (2x),

innocent, calm, welcoming, confirming, formal, hospitable, and cute. The task was to deconstruct the meaning of the chosen experience in order to determine physical auditory features. The students were asked and encouraged to finalize the mind-maps with auditory features so that they could use the results for sound sketching. The students created the mind-maps at their own pace. In Figure 3, a sample mind-map is presented that deconstructs cute in terms of auditory experience. Following section will discuss the results of the sound sketching workshop.

Mind-maps as an inspirational tool (I)

All students created mind-maps to deconstruct a concept in terms of auditory experience. The mind-maps reflected their own idiosyncratic knowledge on the auditory experience they wanted to create. For example, the concept help was studied by seven students; and seven different mind-maps emerged to deconstruct this experience. Students expressed that the mind-maps for sound sketching made it easier for them to imagine sounds and thus they got inspired during the process of meaning deconstruction. Students also found that the last nodes of the mind-maps often referred to similar auditory links. In Figure 3, for example, one can see that ‘high-pitched’ or ‘warm timbre’ were used more than once

Figure 2. An example of a mind-map that deconstructs an abstract concept cute in terms of auditory experience.

as a reference to describe cute sounds. Students found the multiple-occurrence of an auditory property confirming that they were on the right track with the discoveries of auditory links.

Strategies used for deconstructing auditory experience (II)

Several strategies emerged in students' process of translating an abstract concept to concrete auditory features.

Synonymous abstract concepts. It was observed that the main strategy was to immediately understand the underlying meaning of an abstract concept by providing synonymous concepts that are also abstract by nature. For example, cute (see Figure 3) was described as innocent, clumsy, happy, and sweet; or laidback was described as carefree, irresolute, unhurried, and comfortable. The emergence of synonymous concepts often continued three or four consecutive steps until a concrete concept has been found (e.g., see Figure 3, cute > innocent > clouds). The use of antonyms was also observed in the mind-maps. Similar to synonyms, antonyms were also of abstract nature (e.g., calm > relax > active). Antonyms were also indicated as 'not-*' (e.g., laid-back > not attention seeking > in the background > not alarming > cont.). The use of antonyms was perhaps necessary for students to exclude unwanted semantic associations.

Concrete concepts as instances. One salient strategy was to determine a concrete concept with imaginable sensory properties and clear semantic associations (e.g., see Figure 3, cute > innocent > harmless > stuffed animal). The first emergence of a concrete concept served as an instance to the abstract concept in question. After finding an instance, students unfolded its most salient properties (e.g., stuffed animal > fluffy - round shape - passive - formable) and finally decided on which auditory properties to use (e.g., cute > ... > stuffed animal > passive > low frequency). The type of instances occurring in the mind-maps varied. Students mainly indicated instances that actually produce sounds (e.g., cute > clumsy > toddler > laughter). However, some instances were more saliently distinguished by their visual qualities (e.g., cute > ... > clouds > round). After finding these instances regardless of the type of instance they

found, students managed to relate them to the auditory domain (e.g., cute > ... > round > warm timbre).

Metaphors and direct auditory links. In order to determine the instance and its properties, sometimes students skipped the intermediate steps. One strategy was to come up with a metaphor that directly represented the abstract concept (e.g., mature > bass guitar or hospitable > bartender). The occurring metaphors were concrete concepts. In such cases, there was no indication to the discovery of the metaphor; students somehow directly linked the abstract concept to a concrete one. It is possible that students acted out or mimicked being, e.g., mature or hospitable, and matched their feelings to the feelings evoked by a bass-guitar or bartender. Once the metaphor was indicated, students unfolded their salient physical properties; eventually auditory properties emerged as the last nodes.

Another strategy was to directly come up with auditory properties. This either happened after a consecutive elaboration of abstract concepts (help > urgent > short sounds) or right at the first node (calm > slow). Such discoveries of auditory links were not very insightful in terms of meaning deconstruction; however, they suggest that abstract concepts are implicit knowledge in a way that people know what they are but they cannot explain why.

Visual imagery. Students also made use of the visual imagery to support the meaning deconstruction by providing descriptions of the visual property of the instances (e.g., help > danger > blinking colours > red - yellow - green). The visual imagery was also dominant each time a concrete concept / instance and its properties were provided. Students could make use of visual descriptions to come up with auditory properties (e.g., cute > devoted > puppy > soft > low intensity - warm timbre). This finding suggests that auditory and visual systems both contribute the construction of a concept and this concept can be accessed via either system.

Constituents of auditory experience (III)

Concepts can be innate, formed from experience, or formed from other concepts. The mind-maps created at the workshop provided insights into how abstract concepts are represented in both semantic and sensory memories and what type of semantic

associations constitute an auditory experience. In general, it has been observed that meaning construction of an abstract concept happens via perceptual, cognitive, emotion, and behavioural processes. The occurring semantic associations and sensory links indicate this. Furthermore, the occurring mind-maps provide evidence that there is an indirect link between an abstract concept (i.e., a desired experience) and its sensory properties.

It has been observed that abstract concepts have more direct links to other abstract concepts than concrete concepts. In the previous section, these abstract concepts were mentioned as synonyms. Thus, understanding the meaning of an abstract concept is not straightforward; perhaps, there is more than one meaning associated to them. Therefore, elaborating further on the meaning seems to be necessary.

Emotional responses seemed to be part of the abstract concepts and occurred as the early nodes in the mind-maps (e.g., see Figure 3, cute > happy > cheerful). Emotions were sometimes described with or deconstructed by valence (e.g., pleasant) and activation (e.g., relax) dimensions. Just by deconstructing an emotion, students also managed to access to auditory information (e.g., cute > happy > energetic > quickly alternating - short tones - high frequency).

Abstract concepts and emotions occurred as the early nodes. After those, concrete concepts appeared frequently, which are also described as instances. These instances included descriptions of locations (e.g., at home, in the background, concert), time (e.g., immediate, regular pace), actions (e.g., sigh of relief, screaming, drowning), living & non-living objects (e.g., puppy, toddlers, firemen, clock, candy), object properties (e.g., soft, simple, colourful, basic shapes), and auditory properties (e.g., high-pitched, low intensity, medium tone, fade in).

Of all the occurring concrete concepts, the most common instance was the living and non-living objects. Once students indicated such an instance as one of the later nodes, they continued to describe its physical properties in order to find the relevant auditory properties as the last node. Auditory properties were described in terms of spectral-

temporal structure and psychoacoustics. The most commonly used auditory property descriptions were sharpness, roughness, tonality, harmonicity, loudness, intensity, rhythm, temporal regularity, musical scales, high- medium- and low-frequencies, softness, smoothness, timbre, reverberations, etc.

CONCLUSIONS, LIMITATIONS, AND FUTURE STUDIES

Conceptualization of product sounds refers to developing sound-specific ideas, understanding their semantic associations and auditory links, and determining their congruency with other sensory properties of a product. All these activities eventually start with or relate to the intended product experience. Therefore, initially it is important to understand the correlates of product experience in terms of its semantics associations and auditory properties to sketch early ideas for product sounds.

Mind-mapping, therefore, might be a good platform for designers to explore both the meaning of the intended experience and its correlates to product properties by allowing designers to brainstorm about a key concept, discover and connect related concepts in order of importance and relevance, and elaborate further on subsequent key concepts in an inquisitive manner. The overall aim is to encourage designers to actually design sounds by providing them with a creative process that integrates sound conceptualization and implementation and by supporting them with a familiar tool/method such as mind-maps.

One critique often posed by design researchers is whether meaning of any abstract concept would be universally equal to all people. This may create tension in communication between the designer and the user, if the user fails to attribute the same meaning to the product as the designer intended. Fundamentally, the constitution of abstract concepts is idiosyncratic to the person, occurs within a context and is influenced by social factors. However, there are commonly agreed adjectives in language that refer to certain feelings or that describe certain features of an object / person. Some examples are cute, elegant, dominant, tough, friendly, etc. It is such abstract concepts that designers often tackle during conceptual design. According to Govers &

Schoormans (2005), such concepts refer to personality traits that people are well trained to capture and to use to metaphorically describe non-living living objects, e.g., peaceful clouds, happy colours. A future extension of this study could check whether personality traits occur more often than adjectives (i.e., abstract concepts) that describe object features (e.g., simple, harmonic, efficient, energetic) and whether personality traits are easier to understand by the potential users than object features.

Other future studies could use mind-maps in order to further understand the semantic content of the abstract concepts. For example, it would be interesting to observe a single intended auditory experience and systematically analyze the occurring semantic associations. Moreover, it is possible that not all abstract concepts have the same distance in terms of semantic nodes to the concrete auditory properties. It should be checked whether some abstract concepts are easier to more difficult to link to sensory properties. For example, simplicity may refer more easily to product properties than sustainability.

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